

CHARACTERIZATION OF DELAMINATION TOUGHNESS OF ANGLE-PLY GLASS/EPOXY CYLINDERS

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SUMMARY: Delamination growth in filament-wound glass/epoxy composite cylinders is examined. Analysis and experiments on DCB, ENF and MMB specimens machined from the cylinder wall are presented. The beam axis was parallel to the cylinder axis making the cross-section curved, but the beam axis straight. Experiments on beam specimens machined from glass/epoxy cylinders were conducted on $[\pm\theta]_6$ and $[\pm\theta]_{12}$ lay-ups, where θ is the winding angle with respect to the cylinder (and beam) axis ($\theta = 30^\circ, 55^\circ$ and 85°). Fracture toughness data were reduced from experimental data using specially developed beam analysis and experimental compliance calibration methods. It was found that the initiation value of fracture toughness corresponding to crack propagation from the film insert increased with increased mode II fraction, G_{II} / G , and increased ply angle, θ . External pressure tests performed on cylinders with artificial defects and impact damage revealed that the cylinder implosion behavior was insensitive to the presence of single delaminations but impact damage caused reductions in failure pressure.

Keywords: Cylinders, Interlaminar fracture, Mixed mode, Delamination

INTRODUCTION

Glass/epoxy composite cylinders are widely used, designed to resist either internal pressure (e.g. fluid transport and storage, cooling systems) or external pressure (e.g. underwater applications). One of the main concerns with these structures is the propagation of interlaminar defects, produced during manufacture or service. A sound knowledge of the factors affecting delamination resistance of the composites used for cylindrical structures is essential if their safe working envelope is to be defined. The analysis and test methods developed here are necessary for conducting a fracture mechanics analysis of the severity of defects in composite cylinders, and hence provide the basis for a more rational approach to both NDT after manufacture (acceptance/rejection criteria) and to in-service inspection. Several tests have been developed to characterize the delamination resistance of composite materials, see e.g. a recent publication of Davies et al. [1], but such tests suffer from several drawbacks when cylindrical composite structures are considered. The standard test methods are developed

for high-modulus unidirectional composites. Very little work has been done on other types of composite systems and lay-ups, although cylindrical structures commonly involve low-modulus glass fibers and angle-ply laminates. Furthermore, almost all previous work has considered fracture specimens with rectangular (flat) cross-section, while specimens machined from cylinders have curvature in one direction. Riddle and Beckwith [2] tested mode I and mode II specimens machined into flat coupons from thick carbon/epoxy cylinders. Davies and Rannou [3] performed DCB tests on curved glass/epoxy specimens cut from cylinders but analyzed the data using compliance calibration neglecting several details of the curved specimens.

The present project has focused on characterization of delamination growth in filament wound composite cylinders. Delamination tests on beam specimens machined from flat plate and from the cylinder wall have been performed utilizing DCB (mode I), ENF (mode II) and MMB and ADCB (mixed mode I/II) tests, see Fig. 1. For the cylinder wall specimens the test fixture was modified to accommodate the curved cross-section. Analysis is developed to take account of several complexities associated with this type of specimens such as curved cross-section, asymmetry, residual stresses, interlaminar shear deformation and finite geometry effects. Experimental compliance data are compared with predictions from analysis, and fracture toughness data are determined from analytical expressions and experimental compliance calibration data. The mechanisms of crack propagation are examined and related to measured toughness data. Pressure tests on cylinders without implanted defects and with impact damage and implanted defects to simulate fabrication and in-service damage, were also performed.

Materials and Specimens

Glass/epoxy plates and cylinders were manufactured using the filament winding process. E-glass fibers were impregnated with a low viscosity epoxy resin from Ciba Geigy suitable for filament winding. The flat plates were unidirectional, of thickness 4.5 mm. Three series of cylinders have been examined. The machined samples were taken from cylinders with an internal diameter of 160 mm and the nominal wall thicknesses were 6 and 12 mm (12 and 24 layers). The corresponding lay-ups of the cylinders were $[\pm\theta]_6$ and $[\pm\theta]_{12}$, where $\theta = 30^\circ, 55^\circ$ and 85° . A 58 mm long and 13 μ m thick aluminum film was inserted at the mid-plane of the cylinders during the filament winding process to define a starter delamination crack. The initial crack lengths for the DCB, ENF and MMB specimens were 31 ± 2 , 28 ± 3 and 25 ± 1 mm, respectively. The third series of external pressure tests employed smaller (55mm internal diameter) cylinders of lay-up $[\pm 55]_6$ and wall thickness 6.5 mm. These cylinders were cured at 125°C for 7 hours and V_f was measured to be 68%.

After filament winding, the plates and large diameter cylinders were cured at 160°C for three hours. Measured fiber volume fraction V_f was $52\pm 2\%$ for the plates and $61 \pm 3\%$ for all cylinder lay-ups. As illustrated in Fig. 1, curved beam fracture specimens of a nominal length of 200 mm and a nominal width of 18 mm were cut from the cylinder wall for the subsequent DCB, ENF and MMB tests schematically illustrated in Fig. 2. In

order to accommodate the curved cross-section of the beam fracture specimens, contoured aluminum loading tabs were fitted to the DCB and MMB specimens and contoured loading pins and supports were attached to the ENF and MMB test fixtures. The length between the outer supports in the ENF and MMB fixtures was 100 mm.

Figure 1: Beam fracture specimen machined from composite cylinder.

Figure 2: Specimen configurations.

Fracture Testing

Prior to fracture testing of the composite cylinder specimens, their dimensions (width, thicknesses of the laminate (H) and sub-laminates (h_1 and h_2)) were measured, see Fig. 1. Then, one edge of the specimen was painted with white “liquid paper” to facilitate visual observation of the onset of crack propagation and crack length measurements. The position of the initial crack was marked on the painted specimen edge. All fracture tests were performed from the end of the (straight) insert without pre-cracking.

Specimens from unidirectional plates were DCB (initial crack length 50mm), ENF (crack length 25 mm), and ADCB (DCB asymmetrically loaded by clamping the uncracked end of the specimen, free length 110 mm, initial crack length 50 mm and loading only one arm in tension to give a ratio G_I/G_{II} of 4/3 [4]). Five or six replicates were used for each test. DCB, ENF and MMB curved specimens were tested, with two to four replicate specimens for each lay-up. The specimens were loaded in displacement-controlled testing frames. A slow cross-head speed (between 0.5 and 1 mm/min) allowed for visual monitoring of crack propagation. Displacement of the cross-head was measured with a LVDT, and a real-time load (P) versus displacement (δ) response was recorded. The onset of crack growth from the starter insert was determined by inspection of the specimen edge with a travelling microscope during the test and observation of the P- δ response on the chart recorder. The region around the crack tip was observed with the travelling microscope during the fracture test to detect crack jumping and fracture mechanisms for the growing crack. Fracture testing of the curved DCB specimens employed the incremental method proposed by Wilkins et al. [5]. For the curved ENF specimens, compliance measurements were performed at crack lengths of 0, 10, 20 and 30 mm at a small load for all specimens to allow for subsequent compliance calibration.

Data Reduction for Fracture Toughness

Analysis of the flat specimens was performed using the conventional methods, experimental compliance calibration for the DCB [6], beam theory for the ENF [7] and large displacement corrected beam theory for the ADCB [8]. Bending analysis of the DCB, ENF and MMB specimens machined from the filament wound cylinders, Figs. 1 and 2, has been presented by the authors in three publications, i.e. Refs. [9-11]. The analysis is based on first order shear deformation theory for shallow cylindrical shells one-dimensionalized to obtain beam expressions suitable for data analysis of the delamination test specimens. Such analysis incorporates the effect of asymmetry of the delaminated region due to lay-up and thickness, and elastic foundation effects for the finite beam geometries. For details, see Refs. [9-11]. In addition, the experimental compliance calibration method [12] was used to determine fracture toughness of the DCB and ENF specimens. Compliance calibration of the MMB test was not possible and only the beam theory was used to reduce fracture toughness. It was demonstrated that the beam expressions were good predictors of the compliance for the various test geometries examined, and hence produced results consistent with the experimental compliance calibration method. It was furthermore demonstrated that residual thermal stresses had a negligible influence on the fracture toughness results.

Fracture Test Results

The results from tests on flat plates are shown in Table 1 below. Initiation values defined by non-linearity and 5% compliance change on the load-displacement plot are presented.

Table 1: Fracture toughness values for unidirectional panel specimens, standard deviation in brackets.

Loading	G_c^{NL} , J/m ²	G_c 5%, J/m ²
Mode I	247 (13)	316 (20)
Mixed mode	439 (46)	603 (65)
Mode II	1785 (202)	2654 (549)

Inspection of the data reveals a trend where G_c and the scatter increase with increasing mode II fraction (G_{II}/G).

Figure 3: Load-displacement curves for a curved $[\pm 30]_{12}$ DCB specimen.

Figure 3 shows a typical example of a load-displacement ($P-\delta$) curve for curved $[\pm 30]_{12}$ DCB specimens. The DCB specimens displayed initially stable $P-\delta$ response with crack propagation loads increasing with increased crack length, see Fig. 3. After some 20-30 mm of crack extension, however, there was an increment of unstable growth associated with a substantial load drop. Prior to unstable growth it was found that the crack was

temporarily arrested by a interlaced fiber bundle. Such interlacing is inherent in filament wound structures. With some further load application, the crack jumped upwards to another interface and continued to grow until obstructed by another interlaced fiber bundle. In addition to the interlaced fibers, it was found that pull-out of bridged fibers contributed to the fracture resistance and R-curve behavior, see Fig. 4. Figure 5

Figure 4: Resistance curve for a curved $[\pm 30]_{12}$ DCB Specimen “EF” denotes analytical elastic foundation model, and “CC” experimental compliance calibration method.

Figure 5: Load-displacement curve for a curved $[\pm 55]_{12}$ ENF specimen (left) and $[\pm 55]_6$ MMB specimen at $G_I/G_{II} = 0.3$ (right).

shows typical $P-\delta$ curves for curved ENF and MMB specimens evidencing partly stable crack growth, although the ENF geometry is inherently unstable, and the MMB geometry is unstable for mode II dominated loadings [1]. The $[\pm 85]_n$ ($n = 6, 12$) failed in flexure at quite low loads before crack propagation occurred. Also the 12 ply $[\pm \theta]_6$ specimens ($\theta = 30^\circ$ and 55°) tended to produce nonlinear $P-\delta$ response due to matrix yielding or microcracking, and permanent deformation upon unloading [9-11]. The most reliable

fracture toughness data were determined for the 12 ply $[\pm 30]_{12}$ and $[\pm 55]_{12}$ laminates. Figure 6 shows G_c for the cylinder laminates plotted versus the mode II fraction, G_{II}/G (with data for the $[\pm 55^\circ]_6$ laminate omitted). Also included in the graph are the $G_c(NL)$ data for the unidirectional glass/epoxy composite listed in Table 1. The initiation toughness increases with increasing mode II fraction (G_{II}/G) and increased angle θ at the $\pm\theta$ interface.

Figure 6: Fracture toughness, G_c , versus mode II fraction (G_{II}/G).

The fracture toughness data for the unidirectional composite fall slightly below those for the $[\pm 30]$ laminates in Fig. 6. The data in Fig. 6 indicate a trend of diminishing toughness with decreasing ply angle at the interface.

External pressure tests on cylinders

A series of external pressure tests was performed in a 2400 bar pressure tank on 110 mm long cylinders to examine the influence of different types of delamination. In order to simulate fabrication defects that may arise in thick cylinders due to exothermic heating, 50 mm square aluminium foil layers of 13 μm thickness, coated with release agent on both sides, were introduced at different thicknesses in the tube during filament winding. The cylinder consisted of 12 layers and defects were placed between the 3rd and 4th (referred to as 1/4 thickness, 6th and 7th (mid-thickness) and 9th and 10th layers (3/4 thickness and closest to the inner wall)). Cylinders were also tested with impact damage, introduced using steel hemispherical impacters of 34 mm tip diameter and 400 and 600g mass, dropped

from 2 meters height. The apparent hoop stress at implosion is calculated using the expression for thin wall pressurized cylinders:

$$\sigma_{\theta\theta} = PR/h$$

where P is the pressure at implosion, R is the mean radius and h is the wall thickness. Results are shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 7: Hoop stress at failure for externally pressurized $[\pm 55]_6$ glass/epoxy cylinders.

These results show the excellent damage tolerance of this material. The presence of single artificial delaminations covering 12% of the cylinder surface has no significant influence on the implosion pressure. Two hoop oriented strain gauges were bonded to the inner wall of each cylinder, at mid-section, one above the centre of the defect and one on the surface diametrically opposite. At the start of loading, the strain gauges corresponding to the centre of the defects responded differently to those on the wall opposite (without defects), Fig. 8. The gauges over the defects did not react to the pressure at first. Thus in the case of the $\frac{3}{4}$ thickness defect the cylinder was subjected to 75 bars pressure before the delaminated part of the cylinder experiences starts to indicate a compression strain, while when the defect is at mid-wall thickness the load is transferred to the delaminated inner wall section sooner, at 50 bar pressure. As pressure is increased the outer part of the cylinder wall then presses against the the inner delaminated part and there is no further

influence of the delamination, the cylinder behaves as if the defect is no longer present and the slope of the strain gauges with and without defects is the same. The responses of the gauges on the wall diametrically opposite to the implanted defect, and of both those on the ¼ depth defect cylinder (not shown in Fig. 8), superpose perfectly on the strain responses for a cylinder without defects, which is a straight line starting at the origin.

Figure 8: Hoop strain gauge responses, first part of tests for three cylinders with and without artificial defects, two strain gauges per cylinder (over defect and on opposite wall).

When cylinders were impacted at 8 and 12 J, multiple delaminations occurred through the wall thickness. Some cylinders were sectioned and the summed area of the delaminated surfaces after a 8J impact was found to be very similar to the area of the artificial defects (2500 mm²). When the 8 and 12J impacted cylinders were pressure tested local failure occurred, and there was a reduction in failure pressure of around 15 to 20%. These results suggest that for the $[\pm 55^\circ]$ glass/epoxy cylinders examined here, impact damage is likely to be more harmful in service than fabrication defects. However, this may not be the case for other lay-ups and fibres and further tests are underway to examine these parameters.

CONCLUSIONS

An experimental study on glass/epoxy angle-ply laminate specimens machined from composite cylinders was conducted over a wide range of mode ratios. Specifically, $[\pm\theta]_6$ and $[\pm\theta]_{12}$ laminates with mid-surface delaminations were considered, where $\theta = 30^\circ, 55^\circ$ and 85° . Initial, stable interlaminar crack growth observed for mode I dominated loadings was temporarily arrested by bridging of interlaced fiber bundles followed by unstable propagation after crack jumping to other interfaces. The initiation value of mixed mode fracture toughness, G_c increased with increased mode II fraction and ply angle. The $[\pm 55^\circ]_6$, $[\pm 85^\circ]_6$, and $[\pm 85^\circ]_{12}$ laminates were found to be too flexible and weak for successful delamination testing. Cylinders loaded under external pressure were insensitive to single artificial delaminations, but multiple delaminations of similar total area produced by impact caused reductions in implosion pressure.

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